

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Characterization Under Vacuum Conditions

This application highlight addresses the measurement of materials under vacuum conditions using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS).

Figure 1. Close-up of multi-layer insulation from a satellite¹.

Accurately measuring the thermal conductivity of insulation materials, such as foams, aerogels, and other porous structures, under vacuum conditions is essential for applications where convective heat transfer is eliminated, and conduction and radiation become the dominant modes of heat transport. This is particularly relevant in aerospace systems, where spacecraft and satellites operate in high-vacuum environments and require reliable thermal insulation to protect onboard electronics and maintain thermal stability. Cryogenic technologies, including those used in liquefied gas storage, superconducting systems, and scientific instrumentation, also depend on vacuum environments to minimize heat ingress. In these contexts, understanding how insulation materials perform under vacuum enables engineers and researchers to select and design materials that meet stringent thermal performance requirements, ensuring safety, efficiency, and longevity of critical systems.

Insulations have a long-standing history of being tested using steady-state methods, such as the Heat Flow Meter (HFM) and Guarded-Hot Plate (GHP). These traditional methods provide highly accurate measurements and also benefit from the ability to test multilayered samples; however, limitations on sample size, throughput speed and the availability to test under vacuum environments hinder applicability in this application space. Conversely, Laser Flash Analysis (LFA) has introduced vacuum testing capabilities for various applications and can accommodate smaller sample formats; however, due to the nature of insulation materials and their low thermal conductivity values, it is not generally regarded as a suitable approach for testing. So this leaves a performance gap that needs to be addressed.

¹ **Image source:** Wikimedia Commons

Figure 2. Left) Standard MTPS sensor Right) MTPS Pressure Cell for testing thermal conductivity under vacuum conditions.

C-Therm's Trident platform offers a versatile suite of tools for evaluating a wide range of materials, including insulations, under realistic testing conditions, including vacuum environments. The Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) sensor can be integrated into a pressure vessel, allowing for precise thermal conductivity measurements under both elevated pressure and vacuum conditions. Polyurethane foam is an extremely efficient thermal insulator, with a typical thermal conductivity in the range of 0.02 to 0.03 W/mK². The data presented below illustrates the variation in thermal conductivity of a polyurethane foam when tested in ambient air versus partial vacuum conditions.

Figure 3. Thermal conductivity results under ambient and partial vacuum conditions. Data collected using Aerogels calibration with RhoCp input.

As highlighted above, the influence of the testing environment can significantly impact the resulting thermal conductivity measurement (~71% decrease). Conducting tests under conditions that closely mimic real-world applications is essential for obtaining accurate

² Molecules. 2017 Jul 2;22(7):1091. doi: [10.3390/molecules22071091](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22071091)

performance data. This approach ensures that thermal properties are aligned with actual operating environments, enabling more reliable material selection, design decisions, and performance predictions.

About Us:

C-Therm is the world leader in thermal conductivity instrumentation for test and measurement of polymers, ceramics, composites, insulation, textiles, and a wide range of other materials. Headquartered in Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada, C-Therm specializes in non-destructive thermal analysis solutions that empower researchers, manufacturers, and quality control professionals across various industries – from aerospace and automotive to electronics and energy storage.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit
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